

Ternary Extraction and Photometric Estimation of Vanadium(V) with N-Cinnamoyl-N-Phenyl Hydroxylamine (N-CPHAMine) and Thiocyanate in Chloroform

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Vanadium(V) forms a ternary system by mixed-ligand complexation with N-cinnamoyl-N-phenyl hydroxylamine and ammonium thiocyanate at pH 0.95. The green coloured complex absorbs maximum at 580 nm and is soluble in chloroform. The method has improved selectivity and has been successfully applied to estimate the amounts of vanadium in alloy steel and ores.

SYNERGIC effect in chelate extractions are often observed in studying mixed-ligand equilibria systems¹⁻⁴. Such complex formation with thiocyanate ion along with N-arylhydroxamic acid leading to a new photometric method of selective separation and determination of vanadium has been described in this paper.

The reagent, N-cinnamoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine has been found to form a green coloured thiocyanato complex with vanadium in chloroform. The complex absorbs maximum at 580 nm with a bathochromic shift of 50 nm. The molar absorptivity of the complex formed in 0.16 M HCl is 7.0×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 580 nm. Only Fe(III) and Ti(IV) interfere in the determination. The method has been found to be rapid and simple and finds successful application in high speed steel and ore analysis.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions: A stock solution of vanadium(V) (2.2 mg/ml) was prepared from G. R. (E. Merck) grade ammonium vanadate and standardized⁵. The reagent N-CPHAMine (158°-161°) was prepared following the method in literature⁶. Standard solution of the reagent was prepared in purified chloroform. All other reagents and solutions of the diverse ions were prepared from Analytical Grade compounds.

Apparatus: A Hilger-Uvispek spectrophotometer was used for all measurements with 1 cm matched glass cells. An Elico pH-meter model LI-10 (India) was employed for pH measurements.

General procedure: An aliquot of vanadium(V) solution (100 µg) was transferred into a 100 ml separatory funnel, 6 ml of 1% reagent solution and 5 ml of 2% ammonium thiocyanate solution and required volume of chloroform were added to maintain the volume of the organic phase at 15 ml.

The acidity was adjusted to 0.16 M by the addition of hydrochloric acid. The green coloured complex was extracted by shaking the mixture thoroughly for 7-8 min. The extraction was repeated twice with 5 ml portions of chloroform. The combined extract and washings were dried over anhyd. sodium sulphate, transferred into a 25 ml standard flask and the volume was made up with pure solvent. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 580 nm against a reagent blank. The violet binary complex [V(V): N-CPHAMine] in the same solvent showed maximum absorption at 530 nm. The wide bathochromic shift of 50 nm in the absorbance maximum indicated that a mixed-ligand complex was formed when thiocyanate ions were present.

Procedure for analysis of steel: The steel sample (0.5 g) was dissolved in 1:4 H₂SO₄, heated to fumes after dissolution. It was cooled and made up to a volume of 250 ml with acidulated water. An aliquot (2.5 ml to 8.0 ml) of the above solution was diluted to 15 ml with water, oxidized with potassium permanganate solution. Iron(III) was precipitated out with 15% (w/v) NaOH solution for complete recovery of vanadium(V) as sodium vanadate in the filtrate. The vanadium content was estimated as stated earlier.

Procedure for analysis of ilmenite: Finely powdered ilmenite ore (0.5 g) mixed with 9 g of potassium bisulphate was heated and brought to a clear melt. The product was cooled and leached with dil H₂SO₄ containing HNO₃. The mixture was heated and iron(III) and other metals were removed as hydroxides by adding NaOH solution. The volume of the filtrate was made up to 100 ml. The vanadium content was estimated as before.

Results and Discussion

Effect of N-CPHAMine reagent and ammonium thiocyanate: Extractions of the ternary complex in

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM(V). VANADIUM CONC. IN THE EXTRACT 4 µg/ml, ABSORBANCE MEASURED AT 580 nm IN PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT IONS

Ions	Added as	Tolerance limits, ppm	Ions	Added as	Tolerance limits, ppm
Oxalate	Oxalic acid	100	Cr(III)	Cr(NO ₃) ₃	100
Tartrate	Tartaric acid	200	Mn(II)	MnCl ₂	300
Citrate	Na-citrate	1000	Co(II)	CoCl ₂	70
EDTA	Na ₂ -EDTA	500	Ni(II)	NiCl ₂	125
Fluoride	NaF	200	Cu(II)	CuCl ₂	200
Acetate	Na-acetate	3200	Zr(IV)	Zr(NO ₃) ₄	200
Phosphate	(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	2400	Th(IV)	Th(NO ₃) ₄	300
Zn(II)	ZnSO ₄	200	Re(VII)	KReO ₄	70
Cd(II)	CdCl ₂	200	Mo(VI)	(NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄	125(EDTA)
Hg(II)	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	200	W(VI)	Na ₂ WO ₄	60
Pb(II)	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	200	UO ₂ (II)	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	75
Ca(II)	CaCl ₂	500			
Pd(II)	PdCl ₂	250			
Al(III)	Al(NO ₃) ₃	200			

presence of an excess of thiocyanate [5 ml of 2% (2.6 × 10⁻³ M) solution] and different volumes of 1% (w/v) (4.2 × 10⁻⁴ M) solution of N-CPHAmine reagent showed that extraction was quantitative when 6 ml of the reagent was used.

Beer's law, optimum range, photometric error, molar absorptivity and sensitivity: The ternary system obeyed Beer's law from 0.4 to 12 µg/ml of V(V). The optimum concentration range as obtained from steepest portion of Ringbom's plot⁷ is found to be 1-8 µg/ml of the metal (Table 1). The photometric error according to Ayre's equation⁸ was 2.72%. The molar absorptivity of V(V)-N-CPHAmine complex in chloroform was calculated from Beer's law to be 0.70 × 10⁴ l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The Sandell's⁹ sensitivity for reaction is 0.0075 µg/cm² of V(V).

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF VANADIUM(V)-OPHAMINE-THIOCYANATE IN ACID MEDIUM AT 580 nm

V(V) Taken, ppm	V(V) Found, ppm	% Error
0.4	0.39	2.5
0.8	0.78	2.5
1.0	0.98	2.0
2.0	1.95	2.0
3.0	3.01	0.3
4.0	3.98	0.5
6.0	5.90	1.1
8.0	7.85	1.8
10.0	9.80	2.0
12.0	11.7	2.5

Analysis of alloy steel and ilmenite ore samples: A standard high-speed steel (Sample No. BAS-64b) was obtained from the Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Newman Hall, Yorkshire, U. K. and ilmenite ore of Hornbendite rock from Kavur Anchal, Tamilnadu, India, was obtained by courtesy of the Geological Survey of India, Calcutta. Three repetitive extractions were carried out for each of the alloy-steel and ore samples and the V content

was found in each case. The average result is being given in the Table 2.

TABLE 2—VANADIUM CONTENT OF STANDARD SAMPLES

Alloy steel		Ilmenite ore	
% Reported	% Found	% Reported	% Found
1.99	1.96	0.1	0.094

Interference studies: The effect of foreign ions in the determination of vanadium by ternary extraction is given in Table 3. A deviation by 0.005 absorbance from that expected for 4 µg V/ml of the final extract is considered the limit of tolerance. A 50 fold excess of urea and thiourea have been tolerated. Fe(III), Ti(IV), Nb(V) and Ta(V) interfere. Mo(VI) has been tolerated at 50 times excess over vanadium(V) in presence of EDTA as complexing agent. The method has been found to be selective in presence of 50 times excess of a large number of transition metal ions and 25 to 100 times excess of a few anions. All other ions investigated for this ternary extraction have considerably higher tolerance limits.

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